

Notes

Thiocyanato Complexes of Copper(II) with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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THERE is considerable interest in the ambidentate nature of pseudo halide ions, in particular thiocyanate. This ion may coordinate to a metal via nitrogen or via the sulfur atom or it may act as a bridge between two metal atoms (M-NCS-M). A number of copper(II) thiocyanato complexes of the formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2\text{L}_2]$ where 'L' is the above mentioned ligands were prepared to examine the nature of bonding in these complexes. Ethanolic suspension of cupric thiocyanate was refluxed with different nitrogen donor ligands in 1 : 2 ratio for 30 mins. The compounds were suction filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal and thiocyanate by standard methods. Conductance was measured in *M*/1000 acetone solutions using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens using Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP. 200 Spectrophotometer and the electronic spectra were recorded in the Visible Range, using *M*/100 acetone solution and a Unicam SP. 500 Spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion :

All the complexes reported in the present communication have the general formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2\text{L}_2]$; are either light green or olive green amorphous compounds. They melt with decomposition and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they are non-electrolytes, Δ_M values ranging between 8-13 mhos (Table I). Magnetic susceptibility measurements show them to be paramagnetic with μ_{eff} values ranging between 1.78 to 1.9 B. M. (Table I), indicating the presence of one unpaired electron.

Infrared spectra provide evidence of bonding of the nitrogen donor ligands with the metal ion as most of the ligand absorption bands are modified. Absorption bands attributable to $\nu(\text{C-N})$ and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ are given in Table 1. The thiocyanate ion generally co-ordinates to class 'a' metals through nitrogen and to class 'b' metals through sulfur. Criteria for establishing the mode of bonding in thiocyanate complexes have been worked out based on the frequency ranges found for the three vibrational modes of thiocyanate ion i. e., $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{C-S})$ and the degenerate bending mode $\delta(\text{NCS})$. For the free thiocyanate ion as in KNCS these frequencies are $\nu(\text{C-S}) = 743 \text{ Cm}^{-1}$, $\delta(\text{NCS})$ bending = 470 and $\nu(\text{C-N}) = 2056 \text{ Cm}^{-1}$. According to Tramer an increase in the frequency of $\nu(\text{C-N})$ of 50-70 Cm^{-1} relative to free thiocyanate ion is indicative of M-SCN coordination. For M-NCS this increase is only 30-40 Cm^{-1} . A large increase of 70-120 Cm^{-1} is diagnostic of strong bridged complex. For those cases in which is possible to assign unequivocally the $\nu(\text{CS})$ frequency, the difference with the free thiocyanate ion are an increase of 40-90 Cm^{-1} for M-NCS and a decrease of 25-55 for M-SCN.

In the case of complexes reported in the present investigation the $\delta(\text{NCS})$ could not be recorded as it was beyond the limitation of the instrument used. But $\nu(\text{CN})$ and $\nu(\text{CS})$ are near about 2100 and 800 Cm^{-1} respectively (Table 1), indicative of a -Nbonded terminal thiocyanate. This is in conformity with recent work^{2,3} on thiocyanato complexes.

Electronic spectra were recorded in the visible range using *M*/100 acetone solution of these complexes. In case of all these complexes a broad absorption band is obtained in the 17000 Cm^{-1} region indicative of a square configuration^{4,5}. This is also in conformity with the earlier suggestions^{6,7} that four coordinate Cu(II) is characterised by absorption peaks close to 550 nm.

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TABLE 1 : ANALYSES, MELTING POINT, INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA DATA OF COPPER (II) THIOCYANATE COMPLEXES

Compound	M.P. (°C.)	$\nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{C-S})$	$\nu_{\text{max}}(\text{C-N})$ (ϵ)	% of Copper		% Thiocyanate	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2\text{Q}_2$	185	2060 vs	808 vs	17500 (38)	14.35	14.52	26.25	26.52
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(1.\text{Q})_2$	201	2045 vs	822 vs	17800 (40)	14.41	14.52	26.36	26.52
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(2\text{Me. Q})_2^{\text{III}}$	125	2060 vs	820 vs	17500 (41)	13.48	13.65	24.86	25.03
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(4\text{-vinyl py})_2$	192	2040 vs	830 vs	17800 (35)	16.15	16.37	29.59	29.88
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(3\text{-Am. py})_2$	186	2040 vs	790 vs	17400 (30)	17.12	17.28	31.32	31.54
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(2\text{-Am.4-Me.py})_2$	208	2090 vs	818 vs	17500 (35)	15.92	16.07	29.22	29.34
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(4\text{-CNpy})_2$	220	2060 vs	800 vs	17500 (30)	16.24	16.40	29.68	29.93
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(4\text{-Etpy})_2$	205	2050 vs	810 vs	17800 (40)	15.96	16.14	29.18	29.45
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(3\text{-Etpy})_2$	203	2050 vs	815 vs	17900 (45)	15.88	16.14	29.19	29.45
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(3\text{-Clpy})_2$	195	2090 vs	818 vs	17600 (40)	15.47	15.63	28.31	28.54
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{imid})_2$	186	2040 vs	810 vs	17800 (45)	19.85	20.14	36.34	36.77
$\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{bzd})_2$	200	2080 vs	810 vs	17400 (30)	15.14	15.30	27.68	27.92

All the complexes are light green or olive green amorphous; all the compounds melted with decomposition. Q-Quinoline, I. Q.-Isoquinoline, 2-Me. Q-2-methyl quinoline, py-pyridino, Am-Amino, Met-methyl CNI-Cyano, Et-ethyl, Cl-Chloro, imid-imidazole, bzd-benzimidazole.

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Photo Corrosion of 63/37 Brass in Aqueous Solutions Containing Chloride Ions

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THE corrosion of copper in sea water in dark and sunlight has been studied by Korovin and Ulanovskii¹ and they have reported the formation of CuCl film on the metal surface. Effect of light on the kinetics of corrosion of copper has also been reported by Ivan Sekerka and co-workers². They have reported that light energy increases the rate of corrosion but not much attention has been paid to the corrosion rate of brass in aqueous solutions of both hydrochloric acid and sodium chloride.

All experiments were carried out at $40^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$. The results of corrosion kinetics were expressed in terms of weight loss in presence and absence of light (Table-1). The results are also represented graphically in Fig 1. Photo current was measured by the method described previously⁴.

Fig. 1. Graph of concentration vs. loss mg/dm²/day for 63/37 brass in aqueous solutions of hydrochloric acid and sodium chloride. A-63/37 brass in HCl in presence of light; B-63/37 brass in HCl in absence of light; A'-63/37 brass in NaCl in presence of light; B'-63/37 brass in NaCl in absence of light.

TABLE : 1 WEIGHT LOSS DATA ON CORROSION OF 63/37 BRASS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF HYDROCHLORIC ACID AND SODIUM CHLORIDE

Size of the specimen : 3x6 cms

Temperature : $40^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$

Duration : 8 hrs.

Concentration of solution (Molar)	In absence of light			In presence of light		
	Loss mg	Loss mg/dm ²	Loss mg/dm ² /day	Loss mg	Loss mg/dm ²	Loss mg/dm ² /day
	Hydrochloric Acid					
0.1	5.8	16.1	48.3	9.4	26.1	78.3
0.5			63.0	12.6	35.0	105
1.0	9.8	27.2	81.6	16.4	45.5	136
	Sodium Chloride					
0.1	1.5	4.20	12.6	2.2	6.10	18.3
0.5	2.2	6.00	18.0	3.1	8.60	25.8
1.0	3.0	8.33	25.0	4.3	12.0	36.0

In the present work an attempt has been made to study the influence of white light (sunlight) on corrosion rate of 63/37 brass when a photosensitive and semi-conducting films are formed as corrosion products on the brass specimens.

Experimental

63/37 brass specimens were used in all experiments. The specimens were cleaned and polished according to the methods suggested by Champion³. Specimens were degreased in sulphur free carbon tetrachloride. The weighed specimens were immersed in 250 ml test solutions i.e. 0.1, 0.5 and 1M aqueous HCl as well as 0.1, 0.5 and 2.0M aqueous NaCl solutions. The experiment was carried out in duplicate, One of the duplicate sets was exposed to white light while the other was shielded from it. After a duration of eight hours all the plates were removed and cleaned by 5% sulphuric acid solution. The reproducibility of the weight loss data is ± 1 mg.

Discussion

Dezincification takes place when brass is dipped in aqueous solution of hydrochloric acid as well as sodium chloride solution. Both solutions contain Cl⁻ ions which react with copper forming CuCl film. This is deposited on the plate surface which gives a reddish brown film. CuCl is photo-sensitive and a n-type semiconductor, hence produces photo current when white light falls on it. The investigation of photo conduction in single crystal has revealed that holes as well as electrons contribute to photo current at all temperatures. Excitation produced by light beam can migrate before dissociation⁵. In both the cases the colour of the film is brown and when the plate is further exposed to light the colour of the film changes from brown to greenish blue and finally bluish-black. This is in accordance with the property of CuCl. Moreover, when the film is exposed to white light a photo current of 0.38 micro ampere is obtained.